

Supplementary material

A multiscale model of the cardiovascular system that incorporates baroreflex control of chronotropism, cell-level contractility, and vascular tone

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File S1. Default parameters for the PyMyoVent simulations. This file is written in JSON format and was used to initialize most of the simulations presented in this work. (Exceptions are explained in the text). The $M_{para,i}$ and $M_{symp,i}$ limits for each reflex-controlled parameter were defined using the `para_factor` and `symp_factor` variables for the appropriate control. As an example, using the first control in the baroreflex section, $t_{RR} = (t_{active_period} + t_{quiescent_period})$ was initialized at 0.857 s and constrained between a parasympathetic limit of $para_factor \times t_{RR} = 1.754 \times 0.857 \text{ s} = 1.5 \text{ s}$ (~40 beats per minute) and a sympathetic limit of $symp_factor \times t_{RR} = 0.386 \times 0.857 \text{ s} = 0.331 \text{ s}$ (~180 beats per minute).

```
{
  "PyMyoVent":{
    "version": 1.1},
  "circulation":{
    "blood_volume": 4.5,
    "compartments":
      [
        {
          "name": "aorta",
          "resistance": 20,
          "compliance": 4e-4,
          "slack_volume": 0.3
        },
        {
          "name": "arteries",
          "resistance": 20,
          "compliance": 8e-4,
          "slack_volume": 0.3
        },
        {
          "name": "arterioles",
          "resistance": 800,
          "compliance": 1e-3,
          "slack_volume": 0.1
        },
        {
          "name": "capillaries",
          "resistance": 150,
          "compliance": 1e-4,
          "slack_volume": 0.25
        },
        {
          "name": "venules",
          "resistance": 50,
          "compliance": 0.03,
          "slack_volume": 0.5
        },
        {
          "name": "veins",
          "resistance": 20,
          "compliance": 0.08,
          "slack_volume": 2.0
        },
        {
          "name": "ventricle",
          "resistance": 5,
          "slack_volume": 0.065,
          "wall_density": 1055,

```

```

        "wall_volume": 0.1
    }
]
},
"heart_rate": {
    "t_active_period": 0.003,
    "t_quiescent_period": 0.854,
    "t_first_activation": 0.1
},
"half_sarcomere":{
    "initial_hs_length": 900,
    "reference_hs_length": 1100,
    "membranes": {
        "Ca_content": 1e-3,
        "k_leak": 6e-4,
        "k_act": 8.2e-2,
        "k_serca": 8.0,
        "t_open": 0.01,
        "implementation":{
            "kinetic_scheme": "simple_2_compartment"
        }
    }
},
"myofilaments":{
    "cb_number_density": 1.15e17,
    "prop_fibrosis": 0.0,
    "prop_myofilaments": 0.6,
    "k_1": 3,
    "k_force": 1e-3,
    "k_2": 200,
    "k_3": 35,
    "k_4_0": 30,
    "k_4_1": 1,
    "k_cb": 0.001,
    "x_ps": 5,
    "k_on": 2e8,
    "k_off": 200,
    "k_coop": 5,
    "int_passive_exp_sigma": 300,
    "int_passive_exp_L": 70,
    "int_passive_l_slack": 950,
    "ext_passive_exp_sigma": 300,
    "ext_passive_exp_L": 70,
    "ext_passive_l_slack": 950,
    "implementation":
    {
        "kinetic_scheme": "3_state_with_SRX",
        "int_passive_mode": "exponential",
        "ext_passive_mode": "exponential",
        "max_rate": 2000,
        "temperature": 310,
        "bin_min": -10,
        "bin_max": 10,
        "bin_width": 1,
        "filament_compliance_factor": 0.5,
        "thick_filament_length": 815,
        "thin_filament_length": 1120,
        "bare_zone_length": 80,
        "reference_hsl_0": 1100,
    }
}

```

```

        "delta_G_ATP": 70000,
        "thick_wall_approximation": true
    }
}
},
"baroreflex":
{
    "b_setpoint": 90,
    "b_slope": 0.02,
    "k_drive": 10,
    "k_recov": 0.1,
    "controls":
    {
        "control":
        [
            {
                "level": "heart_rate",
                "variable": "t_quiescent_period",
                "k_drive": 0.025,
                "k_recov": 0.1,
                "para_factor": 1.754
                "symp_factor": 0.386
            },
            {
                "level": "membranes",
                "variable": "k_act",
                "k_drive": 0.025,
                "k_recov": 0.1,
                "para_factor": 0.5,
                "symp_factor": 2.0
            },
            {
                "level": "membranes",
                "variable": "k_serca",
                "k_drive": 0.025,
                "k_recov": 0.1,
                "para_factor": 0.5,
                "symp_factor": 2
            },
            {
                "level": "myofilaments",
                "variable": "k_1",
                "k_drive": 0.025,
                "k_recov": 0.1,
                "para_factor": 0.5,
                "symp_factor": 2
            },
            {
                "level": "myofilaments",
                "variable": "k_on",
                "k_drive": 0.025,
                "k_recov": 0.1,
                "para_factor": 2,
                "symp_factor": 0.5
            },
            {
                "level": "circulation",
                "variable": "arterioles_resistance",

```

```
    "k_drive": 0.025,  
    "k_recov": 0.1,  
    "para_factor": 0.5,  
    "symp_factor": 2  
  },  
  {  
    "level": "circulation",  
    "variable": "veins_compliance",  
    "k_drive": 0.025,  
    "k_recov": 0.1,  
    "para_factor": 4,  
    "symp_factor": 0.25  
  }  
]  
}  
}
```


Fig S1: Comparison of Ca²⁺ transients predicted by the Ten Tusscher et al. and two-compartment models. The blue trace (partially hidden) shows the steady-state intracellular Ca²⁺ signal predicted by Ten Tusscher et al.'s model (1) with default parameters. The orange trace shows the steady-state prediction for the two-compartment model (Equations 1 and 2 in main text) used in this work.

Fig S2: Steady-state cardiac cycle with default parameters. The top 3 panels show system-level properties (pressures and ventricular volume) while the lower panels show signals related to calcium transients and myofilament function. The OFF and ON labels describe the status of binding sites on thin filament. The SRX, DRX, and FG labels refer to myosin heads in the super-relaxed, disordered-relaxed, and force-generating states respectively (2).

Fig S3: Baroreflex response to a reduction in the reflex setpoint. This figure is identical to Fig 2 in the main text except that P_{set} was reduced to 50 mmHg at 100 s (second vertical line on each plot).

Fig S4: Simulation showing mechanical alternans on an expanded time-scale. This figure replots a portion of the data from Fig 4 in the main text on an expanded time-scale. Note that the half-sarcomeres shorten over two cardiac cycles and then re-stretch rapidly. This leads to ventricular contractions of alternating strength.

Fig S5: Simulated response to rapid blood loss in the absence of baroreflex control. This figure is similar to Fig 5 in the main text except that the baroreflex has been deactivated. Arterial pressure falls to 66/39 mmHg when 600 ml of blood is removed from the venous compartment.

Fig S6: Simulated response to a rapid increase in aortic resistance in the absence of baroreflex control. This figure is similar to Fig 6 in the main text except that the baroreflex has been deactivated. Myocardial wall stress rises when the aortic resistance is increased from 20 to 220 mmHg L⁻¹ s but arterial pressure drops.

References for Supplementary Material

1. **ten Tusscher KH, Noble D, Noble PJ, and Panfilov AV.** A model for human ventricular tissue. *Am J Physiol Heart Circ Physiol* 286: H1573-1589, 2004.
2. **Campbell KS, Janssen PML, and Campbell SG.** Force-Dependent Recruitment from the Myosin Off State Contributes to Length-Dependent Activation. *Biophys J* 115: 543-553, 2018.